

THE PERFORMANCE OF *Moringa oleifera* SEED POWDER SODIUM CHLORIDE EXTRACT ON NATURAL SURFACE WATER

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to show the performance of *Moringa oleifera* sodium chloride extract on high turbidity natural surface water source (pond) water in the arid zone region of North East, Nigeria. Eight samples of collected high turbidity water were subjected to varying doses of a combination of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder (sodium chloride extract) and the aluminium sulphate (alum). The effluent of the sedimentation tank (into which has been added the raw water and crude sodium chloride *Moringa oleifera* alum extract) was collected and tested for salinity, temperature, colour, turbidity and pH after a period of settling period of two hours. The results show that *Moringa oleifera* crude sodium chloride seed powder extract performs as well as alum as a coagulant. However the results reveal that the use of a filter bed is indispensable when the *Moringa oleifera* active ingredients would be extracted using the sodium chloride (common salt). High total coliform removal efficiency in the slow sand filter medium was achieved after there were initial runs to “innoculate” the filter medium.

KEYWORDS: natural surface water, plant extract, *Moringa oleifera*, turbidity, total coliform, slow sand filter, sodium chloride

INTRODUCTION

Plant extracts and essential oils have evoked interest in recent years as sources of natural substances. They have been researched on for their potential uses as alternatives to conventional substances for the treatment of water, many infection diseases, improvement in animal welfare and hygiene, food production techniques as well as food safety (Simonova *et al*, 2008). Due to their contents of different active substances, natural herbs are being explored as alternatives to antimicrobials. There are different methods of extracting the active ingredients from the plants and the extraction methods may actually affect the efficiency of the extract (Okuda *et al*, 1999; Ghebremichael, 2004).

Potable water is an indispensable requirement for the sustenance of healthy human life. To achieve water potability, treatment is often required. For many developing countries coagulation, flocculation and sedimentation are not feasible alternatives for water treatment due to availability and cost implications of basic chemicals (Yung, 2003). Seeds, leaves, barks, and root extracts of certain plants have been found to exhibit flocculating and/or germicidal properties.

The fractionated crude extracts and three isolated pure compounds from stem bark of *Xylocarpus mollucensis* were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities. The ethylacetate extract (EtOAc) showed promising antimicrobial activities against all the gram positive and gram negative bacteria whereas petroleum ether extract showed moderate activities (Haque *et al*, 2007). Agaie and Onyeyili (2007) investigated the safety and antihelminthic activity of the crude aqueous leaf extract of *Anogeissus leiocarpus* in sheep naturally infected with gastrointestinal nematodiasis using the faecal egg count reduction test. In the faecal egg count reduction test, the extract produced dose- dependent reduction in the faecal egg count.

Pesticides can also be controlled using plant extracts. *Dennis elliptica* (tuba) is one of the sources of bio-pesticides which have an increasing importance in both commercial agriculture and small plot subsistence farming. Rotenone (C₂₃H₃₃O₆) is one of the bio-active compounds from *Dennis elliptica* known to be harmless to plants, highly toxic to many insects and relatively innocuous to mammals (Zubairi *et al*, 2005). The antimicrobial activity of *Cantipeda minima* extract was evaluated against seven microorganisms using the disc diffusion method. The extract showed a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity against all the tested bacterial strains, especially *Enterobacter aerogenes*,

Klebsiella pneumonia, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* (Soetardjo, 2007). The study showed that the extract is a good antimicrobial agent with potential applications in public health against disease.

Mbata *et al* (2008) investigated the antibacterial activity of the methanol and aqueous extracts of *Camellia sisensis* on *Listeria monocytogenes* using agar gel diffusion, paper disk diffusion and microbroth dilution techniques. The results showed that methanol and water extracts exhibited antibacterial activities against *Listeria monocytogenes*. The antimicrobial effects of *Eleutherococcus* extract was observed against coagulase-positive *Staphylococci*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Clostridium* – like species and *Escherichia Coli* in faeces (Simonova *et al*, 2008). The crude ethanolic extracts and essential oils of 14 species of spices were examined for their antimicrobial activity against 20 serotypes of *salmonella* and 5 species of other enterobacteria using disk diffusion method (Nanasombat and Lahosupthawee, 2005). Inhibitory activity of spice oils was greater than that of their own ethanolic extracts. Of all serotypes of salmonella tested *Salmonella typhimurium* was the most susceptible strain to both forms of spice extracts.

The attempts at plant materials and extracts for water coagulation arose through self help by poor people who had no access to ground water. The seeds of *Strychnos potatorium* have been used to clarify turbid water since the first centuries A.D. This is a wild tree and where it was not available, kernels of *Prunus* species and seeds of legumes were used as substitutes. Seeds of *Moringa* species have also been employed as water coagulants (Jahn, 1986; 1988; 1994). The above mentioned seeds contain polyelectrolytes which are responsible for the coagulation properties. The cationic electrolytes of *Moringa* are presumed to act like cations of metal coagulants. The leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were found to show strong inhibitory activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *B. subtilis* (Dahot, 1998). It could be clearly noted that aqueous extract of *M. oleifera* leaves possess significant antimicrobial activity against gram positive and negative fungal species. In the evaluation of the antifungal activity by plant extracts against *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* Penz, extracts of 48 plant species were used out of which *Origanum manjorona* emerged the best having inhibited 96% of the fungus spores germination. *C. gloeosporioides* causes blister spot in coffee trees. (Silva *et al*, 2008).

Moringa oleifera seed powder has been termed a potential heavy metal removing agent due to its oxygen and nitrogen donating carboxylate and amino groups (Sajidu *et al*, 2008). Tannins from Turkish acorns (*Valonia*) was used in water treatment as a coagulant and coagulant aid. Ozacar and Sengil (2002) discovered that *valonia* operated much better as a coagulant aid than as a primary coagulant. Lilliehook (2005) extracted the active ingredients of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder using sodium chloride (NaCl) solution and concluded that extraction with salt increased the efficiency of the *Moringa oleifera*. The sample however was a synthetically produced turbid water. According to Katayon *et al* (2004) synthetic turbid water usually shows a better performance in terms of turbidity removal than natural water although the same dosage of *Moringa oleifera* seed extract is applied on both types of water samples. The aim of this paper is to show the performance of *Moringa oleifera* sodium chloride extract on high turbidity natural surface water source (pond) water in the arid zone region of North East, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Sample collection

The highly turbid water sample was collected from a pond on the outskirts of Maiduguri the capital of Borno State, Northeast Nigeria. Ponds are an important source of water in this region for especially the rural dwellers and the socio-cultural well being of the nomadic cattle rearers due to the short duration of the rainy season and prolonged period of dry season.

Laboratory Procedure and Analyses

A sedimentation tank and a slow sand filter medium were connected in series for the purpose of the experiment. 1M sodium chloride (NaCl) solution was prepared by dissolving 58.5g of NaCl in one litre of water. Ground *Moringa oleifera* seed powder was dispensed into the NaCl solution at the dosage of 1 seed per litre of turbid water in the sedimentation basin. (The weight of one seed of *Moringa oleifera* was approximated to 400mg). Varying quantities of alum as reported in Table 1 were added to the NaCl -*Moringa oleifera* suspension. The NaCl -*Moringa oleifera*-alum mixture was shaken for proper mixing and generation of the polyelectrolytes. This was thereafter poured into the sedimentation tank through a sieve where it was mixed with the turbid water and left under quiescent conditions.

After two hours, the supernatant was channeled to a disinfected slow sand filter where the water was left for ten to fifteen minutes before the samples were collected for laboratory analyses. The physico-chemical analysis were carried out according to EPA (1994) while the bacteriological tests were carried out according to Department of Environment (1982 or 1981?). The physico-chemical parameters examined in the raw, settled and filtered effluents include salinity, temperature colour, turbidity, and pH. The bacteriological parameters determined were Most Probable Number (MPN) of bacteria, total coliform(TC) and differential *Escherichia coli* count.

The eight samples of collected high turbidity water were subjected to varying proportions of a combination of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder and the aluminium sulphate (alum). The total weight of both coagulants at each combination was 400 mg. The combinations and individual weights of each substance are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Varying proportions and percentages of coagulants

Varying proportions and percentages of coagulants	Weight of <i>Moringa oleifera</i> (M.O)	Weight of Aluminium sulphate (alum)
90% M.O and 10% alum	360	40
80% M.O and 20% alum	320	80
70% M.O and 30% alum	280	120
60% M.O and 40% alum	240	160
50% M.O and 50% alum	200	200
40% M.O and 60% alum	160	240
30% M.O and 70% alum	120	280
20% M.O and 80% alum	80	320

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physico-chemical parameters

The effluent of the sedimentation tank (into which has been added the raw water and crude sodium chloride *Moringa oleifera* alum extract) was collected and tested for salinity, temperature, colour, turbidity and pH after a period of settling period of two hours.

A sharp increase in the salinity value was recorded for all the settling tank effluents from raw water values of 1.04 to 1.08mg/l to 8.47 – 8.95mg/l. This is as a result of the sodium chloride used in extracting the active coagulation ingredients. This is shown in Figure 1. These values plummeted when the settled tank effluent was passed through a household indigenous slow sand filter bed. The maximum residual salinity value of 1.97mg/l was obtained for the percentage combination of 20% *Moringa oleifera*(MO) and 80% aluminium sulphate, while the minimum residual of 1.78mg/l was obtained when the percentage combination of the MO and aluminium sulphate was 90% and 10% respectively. This shows that the use of a filter bed is indispensable when the *Moringa oleifera* active ingredients would be extracted using the sodium chloride (common salt). The mean value of colour for the high turbidity water was 13352.5pt/co. The 90% MO and 10% alum combination gave the highest settling tank removal efficiency of 98.85% although the other combinations also resulted in equally satisfactory removal efficiencies ranging between 98.70-98.80 (Figure 2). Despite the appreciable colour removal efficiencies, obtained from the settling tank, the effluent was further polished by the indigenous slow sand filter bed. The least colour removal efficiency value determined for the filter effluent was 99.993% from four combinations namely 50% MO 50% alum; 40% MO + 60% alum; 30% MO + 70% alum as well as 20% MO + 80% alum. The maximum colour filterate removal efficiency was 99.996% given by the 90% MO and 10% alum combination.

Figure 3 shows the turbidity removal efficiencies for the various coagulant combinations. The presented combinations are basically in two categories. The first category includes 90% MO + 10% alum; 80% MO + 20% alum, 70% MO + 30% alum; 60% MO + 40% alum where the quantity of alum is less than the quantity of *Moringa oleifera*. In this category, the alum is regarded as a coagulant aid. Conversely, for the second category combinations, where the alum is of higher quantity than the *Moringa oleifera*, the MO is regarded as a coagulant aid. The turbidity results from the settling tank effluent show that high removal efficiencies resulted where the alum is the main coagulant and MO. is the coagulant aid. The values ranged between 97.38 and 97.45%. On the other hand, while employing MO as the main coagulant with alum as

a coagulant aid, removal efficiency values of between 97.31 and 97.45% were obtained. The results show that MO crude sodium chloride seed powder extract performs as well as alum as a coagulant. On passing the sedimentation tank effluent through the filter bed, the combinations in the first category gave turbidity removal efficiencies ranging between 99.78-99.82% while the second category combinations had 99.79% as the maximum removal efficiency exhibited by the 40% mo + 60% alum and 30% MO + 70% alum combinations. The plot of the pH of raw, settled and filtered water for all the coagulant combinations is shown in Figure 4. The pH of the settled and filtered water remained within the WHO recommended value of 6.5- 8.5 (WHO, 1984). This result is in agreement with Muyibi and Evison (1995), Ndabigengesere and Narasiah (1998) and Katayon *et al* (2004), who observed the pH independence of *Moringa Oleifera* seed powder. In the present study (using crude sodium chloride-*Moringa oleifera* seed powder extract), the pH values remained within the recommended zone in spite of which of the two

coagulants was the main or aid. It is observed that for all the coagulant combinations, the settled

water presented lower pH values than the raw water with the drop more noticeable for 40% MO+ 60% alum and 30% MO + 70% alum combinations. This is expected because finished alum treated water usually needs pH adjustment although in this case the presence of M.O seed powder is thought to have eliminated that necessity (USEPA, 1991).

Bacteriological parameters

The bacteriological parameters examined include most probable number (MPN) of microorganisms, Total coliform count (TC) and the differential Escherichia coli count. All the raw water samples had MPN values greater

than 180 per 100ml of water. The settling tank effluent, as well as the slow sand filter effluents for coagulant combinations of 90% MO + 10% alum, 80% MO + 20% alum and 70% M.O + 30% alum all had MPN values greater than 180 per 100ml. The 60% MO + 40% alum combination had the raw water MPN value of >180 MPN per 100ml reduced to 27 per 100ml. The filter medium further reduced this to 17 per 100ml. Equal quantity of coagulant combinations (50% of MO and 50% alum) had the settled tank residual of 21MPN per 100ml with a resulting filter effluent microorganism residual of 16MPN/100ml. When the percentage of alum was increased to 70% concentration in the coagulant combination the settled tank effluent residual reduced to 8MPN/100ml while the filtrate effluent did not show any microbial presence. A zero microbial residual was also experienced when the coagulant combination was 80% alum + 20% MO (Figure 5).

In Figure 6 is shown the percentage Total coliform removals for the settled water and the filtered water. The minimum values were 25.64% (settled water) and 46.15% (filtered water) for the 90% MO + 10% alum coagulant combination. There was increment in removal percentages for succeeding samples and combinations. The maximum settled tank effluent removal of 81.30% was achieved using the 30% MO and 70% alum combination.

The next coagulant combinations 20% MO + 80% alum had a lower TC removal efficiency of 78.35%. The pattern of total coliform removal for the filter effluent shows that the microbial quality of the water improved with time. The collection of the samples of water and hence subsequent slow sand filter treatment were performed on different days for each coagulant combination. The lowest filter TC removal efficiency was the first sample to be treated by the filter. This is shown in Figure 7. The 7th and 8th runs on the filter bed had 100% TC removal and 100% MPN removal. The 100% MPN and TC removal by the slow sand filter is in agreement with World Health Organisation (1997), which said that in a well operated slow sand filter, pathogen removal may exceed 99%. This is because after a filter has been in operation for some time, a layer of microbes called the schmutzdecke develops near the top of the

sand bed. In this layer predatory microbes attack and consume pathogens in the filter influent water. The percentage removals of earlier filter runs were low because a slow sand filter requires days to ripen and become effective after having been inoculated by micro-organisms (WHO, <http://localhost/cgi-bin/gw>).

Statistical Analysis

(A) Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

A two way analysis of variance (ANOVA) without replication was considered to find the relative effects of differences in coagulant combination and physical treatment processes (sedimentation and filtration) on removal efficiencies of colour, turbidity and microorganisms. The effect of differences in coagulant combination on removal efficiency was only statistically significant at 5% level ($\alpha = 0.05$) for micro organisms with F-value of 85.89 being greater than the critical F-value of 3.79 (Table 2).The effect of differences in physical treatment processes on removal efficiencies was statistically significant at 5% level of significance for all three parameters. The calculated F-value was highest for turbidity (F = 15 286), followed by colour (F=4826.42) and then by total coliform TC (F= 144.35).

Table 2: Results of two way analyses of variance for removal efficiencies at varying coagulant combinations and physical treatment processes

Parameters	Source of variation	Degree of freedom	F-value (calculated)	p-value	F-value (critical)
Colour	coagulant combinations	7	1.084	0.46	3.787
	Physical treatment processes	1	4826.42	3.4E-11	5.591
Turbidity	coagulant combinations	7	0.9018	0.553	3.787
	Physical treatment processes	1	15286	6E-13	5.591
Total coliform	coagulant combinations	7	85.89	3E-11	3.787
	Physical treatment processes	1	144.35	6.3E-06	5.591

This trend suggests that when using MO crude salt extract in combination with alum any increment in the concentration of alum above 10% is unnecessary for colour and turbidity removals. Furthermore the results show that both the sedimentation tank and the slow sand filter medium are necessary for natural water treatment.

Statistical significance for a parameter was established when a calculated value of F-statistic was greater than the corresponding critical F- statistic (tail probability P <0.05).

(B) Regression analysis

Two aspects of multiple regression analysis were considered;

- (1) A consideration of the expression of residual turbidity as a function of pH, salinity, colour and MO seed powder/alum ratio for the settled tank and filter effluents respectively.
- (2) A consideration of the expression of log of residual total coliform as a function of salinity, colour, turbidity and pH for the settled tank effluent as well as the expression of residual total coliform as a function of salinity, colour, turbidity and pH for the filter effluent. The resulting equations are:

$$RT_{STE} = 0.1877pH + 0.5047sal + 0.268col - 0.0872moralumratio + 12.6517 + E \dots (1)$$

$$RT_{FTE} = 0.5807pH - 0.9679sal - 3.2359col - 0.2251moralumratio + 2.7993 + E \dots (2)$$

$$LogRTC_{STE} = 0.0163pH - 0.2374sal - 0.0805col + 0.6991tur + 4.1204 + E \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$RTC_{FTE} = -35357.1pH - 580215sal + 123007.3col - 7980.84tur + 1294060 + E \dots (4)$$

Where :

- RT_{STE} Residual turbidity for settled tank effluent
- RT_{FTE} Residual turbidity for filter effluent
- Log RTC_{STE} Log Residual total coliform for settled tank effluent
- RTC_{FTE} Residual total coliform for filter effluent
- moralumratio *Moringa oleifera* /alum ratio
- RTC_{FTE} Residual total coliform for filter effluent
- E error term
- Sal salinity (mg/l)
- Col colour (Pt/Co)
- Tur turbidity (FTU)

Only one of the variables, Moringa/alum ratio, considered in the prediction of residual turbidity for the settling tank effluent was significant at α=0.05 with the t-statistic being -3.1319 and with a p-value of 0.0166 <0.05. This suggests that only Moringa/alum ratio has significant influence on the residual turbidity. The resulting values of statistical properties are coefficient of determination R²= 0.9842 with an adjusted R² = 0.9631, standard error of 0.1031 and overall F-statistic = 46.72 (p = 0.0049) as shown in Table 3 and Equation 1.

Table 3 Results of multiple regression analyses for residual turbidity(settling tank effluent)

Variables	Coefficients	t-statistic	p-value	Regression parameters
Intercept	12.6517	3.7846	0.00685	R ² =0.9842
pH	0.1877	1.0637	0.3228	AdjustedR ² =0.9631
Salinity	0.5047	1.093	0.3106	Standard error=0.1031
Colour	0.0268	2.0861	0.0754	overall F =46.72(p=0.0049)
Moringa/alum ratio	-0.0872	-3.1319	0.0166	number of obs. = 8

Two of the variables considered for the regression analysis of the residual turbidity for the filter effluent were significant at 95% confidence limit. Of the two variables Moringa/alum ratio had the more significant effect as the value of the t-statistic obtained was – 7.004 (Table 4).This analysis yielded the following values of coefficient of

determination: $R^2 = 0.9862$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.9679$; standard error of estimate = 0.056 and overall F- statistic = 53.7736 (p= 0.004).

Table 4 Results of multiple regression analyses for residual turbidity(filter effluent)

Variables	coefficients		t-statistic	p-value	Regression parameters	
Intercept	2.7993		1.7181	0.1295	$R^2=0.9862$	
pH	0.5807		1.5815		Adjusted $R^2=0.9679$	
Salinity	-0.9679	-0.9959	0.3525		Standard error=0.056	
Colour	-3.2359		-6.1130	0.00048	overall F=53.77(p=0.004)	
Moringa/alum ratio	-0.2251		-7.0041	0.0002	number of obs.=8	

Furthermore two of the four independent variables used in the prediction of residual total coliform for the settled tank effluent were statistically significant at 95% confidence limits. Of the two, colour had the more significant effect than turbidity. The regression parameters were obtained as follows: $R^2 = 0.9678$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.9250$; standard error of estimate = 0.074 and overall F-statistic = 22.577(0.0141<p<0.05) as shown in Table 5 and equation 3.

In the prediction of residual total coliform count for the filter effluent (equation 4), salinity and colour made significant contributions to variations in total coliform count. Turbidity and pH did not significantly affect the total coliform count at p<0.05. Salinity was more statistically significant than colour on the basis of the values of the t-statistic obtained. Values of regression properties obtained were as follows: $R^2 = 0.9499$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.883$; standard error of estimate = 10288.31; and overall F statistic = 14.212 (p= 0.0272) as shown in Table 6.

Table 5 Results of multiple regression analyses for residual total coliform(settling tank effluent)

Variables	coefficients		t-statistic	p-value	Regression parameters	
Intercept	4.1204		1.8641	0.1046	$R^2=0.9678$	
Salinity	-0.2374	-0.6425	0.5410		Adjusted $R^2=0.9250$	
Colour	-0.0805		-6.223	0.00044	Standard error=0.074	
Turbidity	0.6991		3.4856	0.0102	overall F=22.577(p=0.0141)	
pH	0.0163		0.1545	0.8816	number of obs.=8	

Table 6: Results of multiple regression analyses for residual total coliform(filter effluent)

Variables	coefficients		t-statistic	p-value	Regression parameters	
Intercept	12940604.0991			0.00458	$R^2=0.9499$	
Salinity	-580215	-3.6936	0.00772		Adjusted $R^2=0.8830$	
Colour	123007		2.4492	0.4416	Standard error=10288.31	
Turbidity	-7960.84		-0.3128	0.7636	overall F=14.212(p=0.0272)	
pH	-35357.1		-0.6421	0.5413	number of obs.=8	

The high standard error of estimate is presumed to be as a result of zero residual for the 30% MO + 70% alum and 20% MO + 80% alum coagulant combinations' filter runs which could not be fitted into a logarithmic analysis.

A graphical comparison of predicted and measured values of residual turbidity (settled tank and filter effluents), residual total coliform (settled tank effluent) and residual total coliform (filter effluent) are presented in Figures 8-11.

The residuals associated with the valid models (equations 1-4) of the regression analyses were examined for normality. The residuals in the models from multiple regression equations are used to constitute an independent variable of mean zero, gaussian random error term, ϵ with variance, δ (Osinubi and Nwaiwu, 2006). The gaussian random error term, ϵ values are assumed to have a normal distribution. The normality test is usually carried out in order to accomplish a qualitative assessment of the validity of the normality assumption. Standardized residuals were

subjected to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for goodness of fit in accordance with the suggestions of Kleinbaum and Kupper (1978). Table 7 shows the result of the residual analyses. The D_{max} values as well as those of the mean and standard deviation show that the residuals for models predicting settled water turbidity (equation 1) and filter effluent coliform (Equation 3) satisfy the normality conditions of $D_{max} < D_{critical}$ and $N(\mu, \delta) \approx N(0, 1)$. The term D_{max} is the maximum absolute difference D between the values of the cumulative distribution of a random sample of size n and a specified theoretical distribution. The D_{max} values for the filtered effluent for turbidity and total coliform also fulfilled the normality conditions of $N(\mu, \delta) \approx N(0, 1)$ but had D_{max} values greater than $D_{critical}$. The $D_{critical}$ which is the critical value of this difference can be obtained from statistical tables.

Table 7 Results of normality test for standardized residuals

Parameter	Mean	Standard Dev.	Variance	D_{max}	$D_{critical}(\alpha=0.05)$	
Turbidity (settled water)	1.7264E-14 ≈ 0	0.6547 ≈ 1		0.4286	0.1793	0.457
Turbidity (filtered water)	1.43774E-14 ≈ 0	0.6547 ≈ 1		0.4286	0.6183	0.457
Total coliform (settled water)	2.9976E-15 ≈ 0	0.6547 ≈ 1		0.4286	0.3268	0.457
Total coliform (settled water)	2.2628E-14 ≈ 0	0.6547 ≈ 1	0.4286	0.8511	0.457	

CONCLUSION

A study of the effects of crude sodium chloride MO extract with alum in high turbid water was conducted statistically using multiple regression analysis and the two way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The use of crude sodium chloride extract reduced the increment of aluminium sulphate (alum) when used with *Moringa oleifera* seed powder for removal of colour and turbidity. This means that a minimum amount of alum when added to MO seed powder achieves acceptable colour and turbidity removal. The settling tank also should be used alongside a household filter medium as both physical processes significantly affect the turbidity and colour removals. In order to achieve high total coliform removal efficiency in a slow sand filter medium, there should be initial runs to “innoculate” the filter medium. Removal of colour significantly influence turbidity removal in the settling tank but not in the filter bed. Turbidity and colour have a statistically significant effect on total coliform count reduction in the settling tank while in the filter bed, salinity and colour influenced total coliform count removals.

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